

Socio-Economic and Cultural Determinants of HIV/AIDS in Botswana: The Logistic Regression Analysis

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Abstract:

The paper investigates the determinants of HIV/AIDS in Botswana in the changing aspects of HIV transmission using the BAIV IV data. With the use of the logistic regression model, the paper investigates the nature of relationships between; socio-economic and cultural variables; and HIV infection. The sample extracted from the BAIS IV data comprises of both male and female individuals aged between 15 and 49 years. Results indicated that the most important factors that affect the prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Botswana are socio-economic variables. People with the lower level of education (no education and informal education) are the most affected groups, and the higher education level one progresses to, the lower the likelihood of the HIV infection that individual is likely to have. The paper recommends that policymakers should improve the quality of education in Botswana. Efforts should be made to improve the non-formal and primary education levels and include HIV/AIDS as part of the syllabus. Furthermore, policymakers should focus more on job creation measures to reduce unemployment. Getting people out of poverty would help people avoid the practice of unsafe behaviours for survival purposes.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, Socio-economic, Cultural, Logistic regression, Botswana

1.0 Introduction

Compared to the rest of the world, Eastern and Southern Africa recorded the highest number of people living with HIV/AIDS in 2015, which is 52%. It also recorded 45.71% of new infections during the same period and has the highest number of AIDS-related deaths which accounted for 42.7% (UNAIDS 2016). Ten million young people between the ages of 15 and 24 and almost 3 million children under 15 live with HIV (Brummer 2002). Over 50 percent of the people infected with HIV are located in Eastern and Southern Africa alone (Caldwell 2000). Southern Africa, in particular, is considered the epicenter of the global HIV/AIDS epidemic: countries like South Africa, Botswana, Lesotho, Zimbabwe, and Swaziland have the highest HIV/AIDS prevalence rates in the world (Brummer 2002).

The HIV/AIDS epidemic in Botswana has reached crisis proportions and has been declared an emergency by the Government. Furthermore, the Government of Botswana (GoB) has adopted a multi-sectoral approach including the international community in fighting the HIV/AIDS epidemic (NACA 2003). In Botswana, like in most other sub-Saharan African countries, the virus that causes AIDS is mostly transmitted through heterosexual contact. Thus, the age-group 15-49 years is relevant in understanding the levels of HIV in a country.

Botswana has made significant progress in developing and launching several national prevention, treatment and support programmes. For example, the prevention-of-mother-to-child transmission of HIV (PMTCT) was introduced in 1999; the National ART programme was implemented and rolled-out in 2002 and offers ARV free of charge to all its citizens; routine HIV testing was introduced in 2004, and HIV testing was further enhanced through an increase in voluntary counseling and testing centres throughout the country. In addition, the National Orphan Care and Home-Based Care programmes provide important care and support for those infected and affected by the epidemic. The Multiple Concurrent Partnership Programme was launched by the National AIDS Coordinating Agency (NACA) in 2009 to address one of the key drivers of HIV transmission in Botswana overlapping sexual relations with more than one person; the Safe Male Circumcision Program, launched in 2009 by the Ministry of Health with the aim of reducing the risk of HIV transmission in males through circumcision (Ama et al., 2015).

Muvandi and Busang (2005) stipulate that a number of documents on HIV/AIDS in Botswana indicate that there is a number of variables responsible for the spread of HIV in Botswana. Some of the reports suggest

that factors driving the HIV/AIDS epidemic are multiple, intertwined and complex and they have socio-cultural and economic antecedents (NACA 2003). HIV/AIDS epidemic has been ravaging Botswana over a long period of time resulting in the country losing a high number of people across all ages. This has had a negative impact on the country's health, social and economic system. Thus, it is imperative to investigate the factors that influence the spread and increase in the prevalence of the epidemic.

This study aims to investigate the factors that influence HIV/ AIDS in Botswana using the 2012 Botswana AIDS Impact Survey-IV (2012 BAIS IV) data. The findings of this study will advise the policymakers, planners, administrators and health professionals on factors that influence the spread and prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Botswana. This will enable them to come up with appropriate policies and intervention measures that will help tackle the epidemic and probably curb its spread.

2.0 Literature review

Danziger (1994) discovered that there is a close link between HIV/AIDS and family productivity in developing countries. This may be clarified by the fact that in case of any single illness or death related to AIDS, the entire household can be devastated through the pain for the lost one, but also through the funeral costs, the prohibitive medical costs and the family income. For instance, in Rwanda, after the 1994 Genocide, different health systems were destroyed (Soeters, Habineza, & Peerenboom, 2006). Additionally, the different infrastructure facilities were destroyed and there were challenges not only for lack of infrastructure but also limited health professionals who are trained (Bucagu et al., 2012). With the rise of households and individuals affected by HIV/AIDS, there is a significant social impact of the epidemic on the productivity in different economic sectors, such as the health systems struggling to satisfy the needs as well as the social support systems and the challenges faced by the traditional mechanisms of coping (Danziger, 1994).

Reinado and Harnandez (2015) explain the symbolic interactionism theory as a theory that focuses on explaining how people create their own identity and define themselves through their interaction with other people. They state that the most relevant scenarios of this theory and HIV are that 1. Human beings react in one way or another depending on their perception of the object, person or situation they face. 2. The individual adopts an active role in creating meanings. 3. Things do not have an inherent meaning; the meaning of things arises or emerges as a consequence of the social interaction established between people. 4. Meaning are handled in and modified through an interpretive process carried out by the person. 5. Common meanings make communication between human being possible.

The social determinants of health are economic and social conditions that influence the health of people and communities (Commission on Social Determinants of Health (CSDH), 2008). These conditions are shaped by the amount of money, power, and resources that people have, all of which are influenced by policy choices. Social determinants of health affect factors that are related to health outcomes. Factors related to health outcomes include: how a person develops during the first few years of life (early childhood development); how much education a person obtains; being able to get and keep a job; what kind of work a person does; having food or being able to get food (food security); having access to health services and the quality of those services; housing status; how much money a person earns; discrimination and social support (Silva-Santisteban et al., 2013).

Chanda-Kapata et al (2016) estimated the prevalence of HIV among teenagers aged 15-18 years in Zambia and determined whether age, sex, setting, educational level, marital and socioeconomic status were associated with being HIV positive. The HIV prevalence was estimated using a logistic regression model. Associations of social-demographic characteristics with HIV were determined using univariate and multivariate. They concluded that HIV prevalence among teenagers was lower than the overall national level prevalence. The patterns of HIV risk among the young population will require further monitoring in order to identify appropriate tools for intervention.

Tiruneh (2009) examines the relationship between several social, economic, political, cultural, and regional factors and the adult HIV/AIDS prevalence in Africa. With the use of ordinary least squares to test the foregoing relationship in 47 African countries for 2004, Tiruneh found that the most important factors that affect the HIV/AIDS prevalence in Africa are cultural and regional variations. The author recommends that health officials and officeholders must teach the people of sub-Saharan Africa how to avoid and control the viral infection.

Hallandendu (2012) studied contributory factors to the spread of HIV/AIDS and its economic impacts in sub-Saharan African countries. Sub-Saharan African Countries are among the poor countries in the world and they also have the highest HIV/AIDS prevalence rates. Poorly developed extractive industries, distributive trade and services, and the traditional peasant subsistence agriculture typify the contemporary pursuits of most of the poorest countries and are significant contributors to HIV/AIDS. The spread of HIV/AIDS has significant impacts on the health sector, education sector, economy, life expectancy, food production and on the children of HIV/AIDS victims. Hallandendu (2012) concluded that HIV/AIDS, like other infectious diseases (e.g. tuberculosis, cholera, etc), thrive most in poor social economic reforms that make female, in particular, have adequate material resources and for habitually promiscuous males and females to beware and take necessary precautions against the spread of HIV/AIDS.

Ama et al. (2015) described the characteristics of the HIV infected older adults in Botswana and determine how the HIV status of the older adults is influenced by their socio-economic and demographic characteristics. They found out that older adults with secondary education and higher education were respectively, 65.5 times and 1.8 times more likely to be HIV positive. Type of locality had a significant impact on the determination of HIV status of the older adults. There is a significant association between the socio-economic, demographic variables and the risk behaviours (use of condom adherence to ARV treatment). Education, focusing on prevention and education initiatives for HIV and AIDS, including peer education, media awareness campaigns, group workshops, publications for mass consumption, individual and couple counselling is very much desired and should be provided to the older adults (Ama et al, 2015).

According to Kelly (1992, 1995), determinants of educational outcomes after parental death were different for rural and urban orphans. In the urban sample, the socio-economic status of the caregiving family was a significant protective factor: the frequency of dropping out of school following parental death was much lower for orphans in economically better-off families than for orphans in poorer households. Gender had a marginal effect with boys less likely to drop out of school after parental death than girls, and orphans who were dispersed within the extended family upon parental death were less likely to stay in school than those kept together as one family unit. The gender effect was anticipated from the general demographic data in the country which shows a higher school drop-out rate for girls than boys after about the fifth grade of schooling.

Several studies have been carried out to try to investigate the causes, pattern, and factors influencing HIV/AIDS around the world. We can conclude that vulnerability to HIV arises from a coming together of biological, structural (social cultural, economic and political) and infrastructural (programs and services) factors. HIV/AIDS is an imminent public health problem in different countries across the globe affecting not only individuals who are HIV positive but also their families and the social and health systems in relation to productivity and providing necessary care, UNAIDS (2005). However, few studies focused on economic and educational factors, further studies can be done in these areas. Therefore this paper aims to investigate the social economic and cultural determinants of HIV/AIDS in Botswana.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Study design and data collection

The study was retrospective cross-sectional in design and utilized the 2012 Botswana AIDS Impact Survey-IV (2012 BAIS IV) data conducted by Statistics Botswana.

3.2 Description of the variables

Response variable Y: HIV status i.e. a person is either infected with the virus that causes AIDS (HIV status =1) or is not infected with HIV (HIV status =0).

Discrete predictors or factors or independent variables: The predictors' structure employed in this paper assumes that among others HIV status is influenced by the following blocks of predictor variables includes demographic variables (age group, marital status), cultural variables (gender, religion), socioeconomic variables (education, employment status) and behavioural variables (multiple sexual partners, age at sexual debut).

To make the analysis relevant, it is restricted to a BAIS IV sub-sample of women and men aged 15-49 years, who are sexually experienced and whose HIV test results are known to be positive or negative. Second, some of the predictor variables such as age at sexual debut are only relevant to those people who have had sex.

The predictors are outlined below:

X₁: Age groups (5 years age group between 15-49 years)

X₂: Marital status (married, never married, living together, separated, divorced, and widowed)

X₃: Religion (Christian, Non-Christian, no religion))

X₄: Education (None, non-formal, primary school, junior certificate, senior school, higher education)

X₅: Employment (employed, unemployed, student)

X₆: Sexual practices (one partner, multiple partners)

X₇: Sexual debut (10-14, 15-19, 20-24 years)

Cultural and behavioural variables are used as control variables for the model.

3.3 Statistical modelling and data analysis

Two analytical techniques are employed namely, tabular and multivariate analysis. The multivariate analytical technique used is binary hierarchical logistic regression. Logistic regression is an appropriate analytical technique given the dichotomous nature of the outcome variable, that is, HIV status. A person is either infected with the virus that causes AIDS (HIV status = 1) or is not infected with HIV (HIV status = 0). The analysis under this study is carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.

3.4 Logistic regression model

Binary logistic regression model: The standard model for the binary nature of the outcome variable is the binary logistic regression model which is a non-linear regression model. One of the main applications of logistic regression is to determine or forecast the chance of occurrence of a particular outcome of the response variable on the basis of independent or explanatory variables by fitting a given data to a logit function. The binary logistic regression is taken to examine the effects of age, education, religion, marital status, sexual practices, employment status and sexual debut to HIV status. To facilitate interpretation, the logistic coefficients is presented as the Odds Ratios (OR), these are the exponentials of the estimates (β 's). The Odds Ratios gives an estimate of the magnitude of the association between the variables being compared.

For binary response Y_j and qualitative explanatory variable X_{ij} , $i=1, 2, \dots, p$ and $j=0, 1, \dots, n-1$,

Where,

p is the number of predictor variables included in the model

n is the number of observations

Let $\pi_j = P(X_{ij})$ represent the success probability when X_{ij} takes the values x_{ij} . We apply the logit transformation where the transformed quantity $\ln\left(\frac{\pi_j}{1-\pi_j}\right)$ lies in the interval $(-\infty, \infty)$ and is modelled as:

$$\text{logit}(\pi_j) = \ln\left(\frac{\pi_j}{1-\pi_j}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1j} + \beta_2 X_{2j} + \dots + \beta_p X_{pj} \quad (1)$$

This can be re-written as:

$$\pi_j = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1j} + \beta_2 X_{2j} + \dots + \beta_p X_{pj})}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1j} + \beta_2 X_{2j} + \dots + \beta_p X_{pj})} \quad (2)$$

where,

- β_0 is the intercept term
- β_i represents the regression coefficients, $i=1,2,\dots,p$
- X_{ij} 's are the explanatory variables

Logistic regressions for categorical predictors - Since the categorical predictors are going to be used in this study, logistic regressions for categorical predictors are presented below:

Suppose the model has a binary response Y and p predictors X_i , $i=1,2,\dots,p$. The predictors can either be continuous or categorical.

$$X_{ij}^r, i = 1,2, \dots, p; \text{ and } j = 0,1, \dots, n - 1 \text{ and } r = 1,2, \dots, k_l - 1$$

where,

- p is the number of variables included in the model
- n is the number of observations
- X_{ij}^r refers to the r^{th} level of a factor

Note that r superscript is merely a label and do not represent a power. Assume that one level of each factor is taken as a reference category, therefore the model will have $(k_l - 1)$ dummies as shown below:

$$P(Y = 1) = \beta_0 + \{\beta_1^1 X_{1j}^1 + \beta_1^2 X_{1j}^2 + \dots + \beta_1^{k_1-1} X_{1j}^{k_1-1}\} + \{\beta_1^1 X_{2j}^1 + \beta_1^2 X_{2j}^2 + \dots + \beta_1^{k_2-1} X_{2j}^{k_2-1}\} + \dots + \{\beta_1^1 X_{pj}^1 + \beta_1^2 X_{pj}^2 + \dots + \beta_1^{k_l-1} X_{pj}^{k_l-1}\} \quad (3)$$

3.4.1 Model selection

The independent variables will be included in the model using a backward regression selection whereby all variables will be included in the model at first. At each step, the variable that is the least significant is removed. This process continues until no non-significant variables remain. The advantage of this model selection is that it retains a large R square value.

With the use of equation (1), three general logistic regression models will be built and analysed. In all the models, the first group is taken as a reference category. The general models include all selected variables in the model and analyse the effects of each explanatory variable on the odds of being infected by the epidemic. The general models can be expressed as:

Model 1: this is the general model including all significant variables selected by backward regression selection. It examines the impact of all variables on HIV status. The model is as follows:

$$\text{logit}(\pi_j) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1j} + \beta_2 X_{2j} + \beta_3 X_{3j} + \beta_4 X_{4j} + \beta_5 X_{5j} + \beta_6 X_{6j} + \beta_7 X_{7j} \quad (4)$$

Where $\pi_j = P(X_{ij})$ is the probability of being HIV positive

- β_0 is a constant
- β_i , $i=1, 2 \dots 7$ are the regression coefficients.
- X_{ij} 's, $i=1,2,\dots,7$, $j=0,1,\dots,n-1$ are either continuous or categorical independent variables in the model.

Each independent variable used in the study has different levels. Age has 7 levels, Marital status has 5 levels, Religion, Education, Employment status, Sexual partners and Sexual debut has 3, 5, 3, 2 and 3 levels respectively.

Model 2: examines the impact of the cultural factors on HIV status, this is made up of religion only. The model is below:

$$\text{logit}(\pi_j) = \beta_0 + \beta_3 X_{3j} \quad (5)$$

Model 3: examines the impact of socio-economic factors (i.e. the level of education achieved and employment status) on the HIV status. Thus:

$$\text{logit}(\pi_j) = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_{4j} + \beta_5 X_{5j} \quad (6)$$

To fit these models, IBM SPSS Statistics 20 software was used.

3.4.2 Likelihood-ratio test

The likelihood-ratio statistic $-2(L_0 - L_1)$ tests whether certain model parameters are zero by comparing the log likelihood L_1 for the fitted model M_1 with L_0 for model M_0 . Denote this statistic for testing M_0 , given that M_1 holds, by $G^2(M_0|M_1)$. The goodness-of-fit statistic $G^2(M)$ is a special case in which $M_0 = M$ and M_1 is the saturated model. In testing whether M fits, we test whether all parameters in the saturated model but not in M equal zero. The asymptotic degrees of freedom (df) is the difference in the number of parameters in the two models, which is the number of binomials modelled minus the number of parameters in M .

Let L_S denote the maximized log likelihood for the saturated model. The likelihood-ratio statistic for comparing models M_1 and M_0 is

$$G^2(M_0|M_1) = -2(L_0 - L_1) = -2(L_0 - L_S) - [-2(L_1 - L_S)] = G^2(M_0) - G^2(M_1) \quad (7)$$

The test statistic comparing the two models is identical to the difference in G^2 goodness-of-fit statistics (deviances) for the two models (Agresti 2002). Conversely, the logarithm of the likelihood ratio will be taken to get the log likelihood ratio.

3.4.3 Significance test

The overall significance of the model is tested using the deviance and the significance of the regression coefficient is tested using the Wald T ratio. $H_0: \beta=0$ and $H_1: \beta \neq 0$

$$\text{The test statistic: } W = \frac{|\beta|^2}{SE(\beta)} \quad (8)$$

Where: $W \sim \chi_1^2$

If for a particular explanatory variable, or group of explanatory variables, the Wald test is significant, then it concludes that the parameters associated with these variables are not zero, so that the variable should be included in the model. If the Wald test is not significant then these explanatory variables can be omitted from the model.

3.4.4 Goodness of fit

The measure of the goodness of fit used here is the count R^2 , which is defined as

$$\text{Count}R^2 = \frac{\text{Number of correct prediction}}{\text{Total number of observations}} \quad (9)$$

Since the regress and in the Logit model takes a value of 1 or 0, if the predicted probability is greater than 0.5, we classify that as 1 activity, if it is less than 0.5, we classify that as 0 activity. We then count the number of correct predictions and compute count R^2 .

3.4.5 Pearson contingency coefficient

If we have N observations with two variables where each observation can be classified into one of R mutually exclusive categories for variable one and one of C mutually exclusive categories for variable two, then a cross-tabulation of the data results in a two-way contingency table (also referred to as an $R \times C$ contingency table). The resulting contingency table has R rows and C columns.

A common question with regards to a two-way contingency table is whether we have independence. By independence, we mean that the row and column variables are not associated (i.e., knowing the value of the row variable will not help us predict the value of column variable and likewise knowing the value of the column variable will not help us predict the value of the row variable).

A more technical definition for independence is that

$$P(\text{row } i, \text{column } j) = P(\text{row } i) * P(\text{column } j) \text{ for all } i, j$$

The standard test statistic for determining independence is the chi-square test statistic:

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

One criticism of this statistic is that it does not give a meaningful description of the degree of dependence (or strength of association). That is, it is useful for determining whether there is dependence. However, since the strength of that association also depends on the degrees of freedom as well as the value of the test statistic, it is not easy to interpret the strength of association.

The Pearson's contingency coefficient is one method to provide an easier to interpret measurements of the strength of association. Specifically, it is:

$$\text{Pearson's Coefficient} = \sqrt{\frac{T}{N+T}} \quad (11)$$

where,

T = the chi-square test statistic given above

N = the total sample size

So this statistic basically scales the chi-square statistic to a value between 0 (no association) and 1 (maximum association). It has the desirable property of scale invariance. That is, if the sample size increases, the value of Pearson's contingency coefficient does not change as long as values in the table change the same relative to each other.

4.0 Results presentation and analysis

4.1 Percent distribution of HIV positive respondents according to socio-economic and demographic characteristic

Table 1 portrays the HIV status of people of both male and females aged between 15-49 years living in Botswana. Several factors are observed too which include the demographic, cultural, socio-economic and behavioural factors. The overall HIV prevalence rate of people aged between 15-49 years is 2.4%, with males having the HIV prevalence rate of 19.5% and females having the HIV prevalence rate of 26.5%. Among the males, those aged 20-24 years have the lowest HIV prevalence rate (4.6%) while the males aged between 45-49 years have the highest HIV prevalence rate (50.6%). In the female groups, those aged between 15-19 years have the lowest HIV prevalence rate and those aged between 35-39 years have the highest HIV prevalence rate (that is 4.0% and 47.4% respectively).

Focusing on marital status, males who are divorced have the lowest HIV prevalence rate and males who are separated recorded the highest HIV prevalence rate (10.1% and 69.1% respectively). Married females have the lowest HIV prevalence rate (18.6%) and widowed females have the highest (40.2%) HIV prevalence rate. Combining both males and females the widowed group have the highest HIV prevalence rate (40.9%) and those who are never married have the lowest HIV prevalence rate (16.6%).

The Christians have the lowest HIV prevalence rate across all the levels, i.e., Christian males have the HIV prevalence rate of 17.5%, Christian females have the HIV prevalence rate of 23.7% and both males and females combined recorded the HIV prevalence rate of 21.1%. Non-Christian males have the highest HIV prevalence rate of 24.7% while females with no religion have the highest HIV prevalence rate of 25.2%. Both non-Christian males and females have the highest HIV prevalence rate (24.6%).

People with higher education have the lowest HIV prevalence rate (13.0%), males with higher education too have the lowest HIV prevalence rate (9.8%) and females with a senior secondary certificate have the lowest HIV prevalence rate (15.6%). Females with a junior certificate have the highest HIV prevalence rate of 31.0% males with no education have the highest HIV prevalence rate of 28.3%. In total, the people with a junior certificate have a prevalence rate of 26.1%.

The students have the lowest HIV prevalence rate with 9.3% when combined, 6.4% among males only and 11.4% among the females. The unemployed people have the highest prevalence rate among the females and when combined (32.2% and 29.0% respectively). Employed males have a prevalence rate of 25.9%.

People with multiple concurrent partnerships have the lowest prevalence while those with one partner have the highest prevalence. People who started sexual activity at ages 10-14 years have a prevalence rate of 0% while those who started at ages 15-19 years have a prevalence rate of 11.4%.

Table 1: Results of HIV Status by Gender and Ages 15-49 Years

Variable characteristic	HIV Status % Positive		
	Male	Female	Total
Age			
15-19	4.9	4.0	4.4
20-24	4.6	15.1	10.5
25-29	12.4	26.1	20.4
30-34	27.9	42.8	35.8
35-39	34.7	47.4	41.8
40-44	43.0	38.9	40.7
45-49	50.6	40.5	44.4
Overall	19.5	26.5	23.4
Marital Status			
Married	25.9	18.6	21.6
Never married	12.4	20.3	16.6
Living together	33.2	34.0	33.7
Separated	69.1	33.7	38.9
Divorced	10.1	32.2	26.9
Widowed	44.9	40.2	40.9
Overall	18.7	23.8	21.6
Religion			
Christian	17.5	23.7	21.1
Non-Christian	24.7	24.4	24.6
No Religion	22.4	25.2	23.6
Overall	18.7	23.8	21.6
Education			
None	28.3	21.6	25.1
Non- formal	14.5	29.5	25.3
Primary	23.9	25.1	24.5
Junior secondary	19.2	31.0	26.1
Senior secondary	10.6	15.6	13.6
Higher	9.8	15.7	13.0
Overall	18.7	23.8	21.6
Employment status			
Employed	25.9	28.9	27.4
Unemployed	23.5	32.2	29.0
Student	6.4	11.4	9.3
Overall	17.4	21.9	19.9
Sexual practice			
Multiple concurrent	15.8	24.0	18.1
One partner	26.7	28.9	28.1
	24.2	28.6	26.6
Sexual debut			
10-14			
15-19	5.2	14.9	11.4
20-24	1.1	13.7	7.4
Overall	3.8	14.6	10.3

The results show that there is a significant association between the variables and HIV status ($p < 0.01$). There is a moderate association between age, employment marital status, and sexual behaviour (sexual partners and sexual debut) and HIV status. There is a weak association between education and HIV status; and a very weak association between religion and HIV status.

Table 2: Summary of Analyses of Inter-Relationship between Variables (ungrouped) and HIV Status

Variable vs HIV Status	Chi-Square	df	P-Value	Contingency Coefficient
Age	85293.96	12	0.000	0.342
Employment	37818.403	4	0.000	0.228
Religion	533.735	4	0.000	0.025
Education	18143.201	10	0.000	0.145
Marital Status	28068.326	10	0.000	0.180
Sexual Partners	3190.869	2	0.000	0.180
Sexual Debut	582.467	4	0.000	0.165

4.2 Interpreting the Logistic regression results

Table 3: The Impact of Demographic, Cultural, Socio-economic and Behavioural Factors on HIV status of People aged 15-49 years in Botswana (Model 1)

Predictors	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig	Odd Ratio (OR) =Exp(B)
Age						
15-19						1.000
20-24	0.448	0.055	66.231	1	0.000***	1.565***
Education				5	0.000***	
None						1.000
Non-formal	1.907	3327.237	1304.254	1	1.000	6.735
Primary	19.919	1532.566	0.000	1	0.990	4.474
Junior certificate	20.056	1532.566	0.000	1	0.990	5.129
Senior school	17.983	1532.566	0.000	1	0.991	6457
Higher education	0.625	1556.546	0.000	1	1.000	1.867
Religion			106.573	2	0.000***	
Christians						1.000
Non-Christians	0.349	0.040	77.321	1	0.000***	1.417
No Religion	-.010	.069	0.023	1	0.881	0.990
Marital Status			630.709	2	0.000***	
Married						1.000
Never married	-0.134	0.123	1.171	1	0.279	0.875
Living together	-1.266	0.129	95.951	1	0.000***	0.282
Sexual Partners						
One						1.000
Multiple	3.143	0.127	610.542	1	0.000***	23.170
Employment Status			1055.437	2	0.000***	
Employed						1.000
Unemployed	1.015	0.042	592.541	1	0.000***	2.760
Student	-1.007	0.074	186.926	1	0.000***	0.365
Sexual Debut			405.932	2	0.000***	
10-14						1.000
15-19	0.377	0.181	4.336	1	0.037*	1.547
20-24	-0.625	0.186	11.341	1	0.001**	0.535

Table 3 shows the logistic regression model including all the variables used in this study. According to this table, the odds of being infected with HIV/AIDS in the ages between 20-24 years are significantly almost twice compared to those aged 15-19 years (OR=1.565, $p < 0.001$). The non-Christians are almost equally likely to be HIV positive than the Christians (OR=1.417, $p < 0.001$). People who are living together are significantly less likely to be infected by HIV/AIDS compared to people who are married. People with multiple concurrent partners are 23 times significantly more likely to be HIV positive than people with one partner. People who started sexual activities at ages 15-19 years are almost 2 times more likely to be HIV positive than those who started at ages 10-14 years. Those who started engaging in sexual activities at ages 20-24 are significantly less likely to be infected than the reference category (OR=0.535 and $p < 0.01$). Education is not statistically significant.

Table 4: The Impact of Cultural Factors on the HIV status of People in Botswana (Model 2)

Predictors	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig	Odd Ratio (OR) =Exp(B)
Religion			483.134	2	0.000***	
Christians						
Non-Christians	-0.141	0.009	250.626	1	0.000***	0.868
No Religion	0.050	0.014	12.969	1	0.000***	1.051

The non-Christians are significantly less likely to be HIV positive compared to the Christians (OR=0.868). People with no religion are equally likely to be infected by HIV/AIDS (OR=1.051). Christians engage in risky behaviours like multiple sexual partners and alcohol abuse with the belief that their sins will be forgiven. This puts them at a greater risk of being HIV positive compared to non-Christians.

Table 5: The Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on HIV status of People in Botswana (Model 3)

Predictors	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig	Odd Ratio (OR) =Exp(B)
Education			15301.456	5	0.000***	
None						1.000
Non-formal	0.849	0.014	3894.168	1	0.000***	6.008
Primary	1.371	0.040	1198.574	1	0.000***	3.939
Junior certificate	1.046	0.011	8997.069	1	0.000***	1.846
Senior school	0.956	0.010	8387.202	1	0.000***	1.758
Higher education	0.155	0.013	149.873	1	0.000***	0.845
Employment Status			38795.111	2	0.000***	
Employed						1.000
Unemployed	1.510	0.008	34279.419	1	0.000***	4.837
Student	1.425	0.009	26886.036	1	0.000***	1.616

Focusing on the impact of socio-economic factors on HIV status in Botswana, we discover that people with non-formal education are 6 times more likely to be HIV positive than people with no education. Those with primary education are almost 4 times more likely to be HIV compared to the reference category. People with Junior Certificate and those with Senior school education are almost 2 times more likely to be HIV positive compared to those with no education (OR=2.846 and OR=2.602 respectively, p<0.001). Those with higher education are less likely to be HIV compared to the reference category. Table 6 shows that as people get more educated, the HIV infection reduces.

The unemployed people are almost 5 times more likely to be HIV positive compared to the employed people (OR=4.837 and p<0.001). The students are significantly almost 2 times more likely to be HIV positive than the employed people.

Table 8: Comparing the Models

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Log Likelihood ratio test	-57.611	-88.065	-25.054

The table above indicates that model 3 is the best model at predicting the impact of HIV status in Botswana. Model 2 and model 1 follows sequentially. We, therefore, can make conclusions that the most fuelling factors of HIV/AIDS in Botswana are the socio-economic factors.

5.0 Conclusions and recommendations

People with non-formal education showed the highest likelihood of being HIV positive. This is fuelled by the education they get from the non-formal sector as they are only being taught how to read and write. As people move to higher education levels, the odds of being HIV positive reduces. This indicates that quality education plays a major role in people’s behaviour towards HIV/AIDS. With little or no education, chances are high that people in these categories will be infected by the HIV virus.

Although Christianity condemns prostitution and pre- and extramarital sex, there is far less enforcement of these views by the Christian society (Caldwell 2000; Brockerhoff and Biddlecom 1999). Many people in this religion engage in adulterous relationships and pre-marital sexual activities as these are not a punishable crime in the Christian societies. This is reflected in the study as non-Christians are less likely to be HIV positive compared to Christians.

The unemployed are more likely to be infected by HIV/AIDS. As they have little or no income to sustain their everyday life, majority of them end up indulging in unsafe sexual activities, others end up being drug addicts as the frustrations of lack of income drive them to the extremes. They end up sharing needles when in the acts of injecting drugs into their body systems, increasing the chances of getting HIV from such needles.

Being frustrated by the state of being unemployed, others end up giving in sexual favours to the potential employers in return for a vacancy. Other opts to engage in adulterous relationships with rich men or women in exchange for material things and money. Prostitution is also an easy option for the unemployed to make quick money. Thus, unemployment is a frustrating and unsatisfying position to be in therefore, many people

who are unemployed end up settling for desperate measures which their employed colleagues may never settle for.

Also, students are more likely to engage in risky sexual behaviours thereby getting infected by HIV/AIDS. With a lot of exposure to alcohol and drug abuse, sharing needles in such mental states, peer pressure, and teenage pregnancy to name a few, students are prone to be targets of this disease.

It is recommended that policymakers should improve the quality of education in Botswana. Efforts should be made to improve the non-formal and primary education levels and include HIV/AIDS as part of the syllabus. Similarly, health officials should teach people how to avoid and control the viral infection. Furthermore, policymakers should focus more on job creation measures to reduce unemployment. Getting people out of poverty would help people avoid the practice of unsafe behaviours for survival purposes. Further studies can focus more on using individual data as findings may reveal what makes people susceptible to HIV infection.

6.0 Limitation of the Study

Among others, one limitation is that this study is based on cross-sectional data so we are unable to detect causality but the only association between the dependent variable and the included explanatory variables. Future studies thus can use time-series data. However, the results do show the significant determinants of HIV/ AIDS in Botswana.

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